

Study of the Influence of Perpres no. 12/2021 on Packaging of Construction Works in Tanah Laut Regency

Gusti Noviar Kusuma¹, Henry Wardhana²
Civil Engineering Study Program, Engineering Faculty,
University of Lambung Mangkurat

Abstract:- Tanah Laut Regency is one of the areas most severely affected by floods in South Kalimantan in 2021. Looking at the tender announcement process for handling post-flood disasters that hit Tanah Laut Regency, there are significant differences from several construction works that are being tendered. There are significant changes in Perpres No 12 / 2021 regarding the limit on the packaging value of the procurement of construction services for small and micro businesses to be six times the previous value. Based on the results of the study, there are variables, namely cost, risk complexity, and technology.

Based on the results of the study, the validity test was tested by comparing the correlation coefficient of Spearman's rank with the critical value concerned with the Spearman Rank coefficient (R) greater than the critical value ($R_{0.05} = 0.37$) concluded that all items were valid. The reliability test was carried out by comparing Cronbach's alpha (α) with a minimum value of reliability with a value of > 0.60 with the conclusion that all data were reliable. This strategy of increasing influence/satisfaction/understanding is based on improving the indicators of the lowest value in each variable so that the packaging of construction work does not only mention the amount of cost and complexity but also pays attention to the risk and technology parameters in packaging the PBJP planning.

Keywords:- Packaging, Risk, Technology, Cost, Complexity.

I. INTRODUCTION

Tanah Laut Regency is one of the areas most severely affected by the flash flood that occurred in January 2021 in South Kalimantan Province. Some of the affected districts are Pelaihari District, Panyipatan District, Takisung District, Kurau District and Bumi Makmur District, and Bati-Bati District. Residents were evacuated to several villages where evacuation posts and public kitchens had been established. Connecting access to Pelaihari City was also cut off due to a broken bridge in Pelaihari District. This condition received the attention of the Minister of PUPR to review the location points affected by the flood for further handling of the impact of flooding in the affected areas, as for the picture of the visit of the Minister of PUPR at the location of the break in the Pabahanan bridge.

Seeing these conditions, it is necessary to handle certain criteria conditions by packaging construction work as a form of handling these conditions quickly but must be appropriate as part of the preparation of PBJP planning in accordance with the provisions of PerpresNo. 12 of 2021 concerning PBJP. As a step in handling this condition, the packaging of post-flood construction work has been carried out by the Tanah Laut Regency Government which can be seen in the announcement process for handling post-flood handling tenders in Tanah Laut Regency. There are significant differences seen from several construction works that are being tendered with a value that is within the limits of the previous regulation, which is more than Rp. 2.500,000,000,- to be packaged for providers of goods/services qualifications for small businesses and in other tender announcement processes the amount of this value is intended for providers with non-small business qualifications, it can be seen in the several work packages announced. (LPSE Kab.Tanah Laut, 2021) in which the Implementation of construction development that is both intended for handling post-flood disasters that hit Tanah Laut Regency.

Based on the determination of the construction service packaging segmentation for post-flood handling in which the announcement delay of the tender process is only 20 calendar days apart and there is a transition or transition of rules which has been enacted, Regulation of the Government Goods/Services Procurement Policy Agency No. 12 of 2021 concerning Guidelines for the Implementation of PBJP through Providers can be seen that the level of the dominant cost is the main variable and even the single variable in determining the construction service packaging segmentation and will be the subject of discussion in the construction work packaging study material. With the significant changes in Perpres No. 12/2021 related to the limit on the packaging value of the procurement of construction services for small and micro businesses to be six times the previous value which was only Rp. 2,500,000,000. to be Rp. 15,000,000,000, (Mustafa, 2021) will certainly have a major impact on the implementation of the construction, even though Law No. 2 of 2017 and its implementing regulations, namely PP. 22 of 2020 mentions 3 elements in determining market segmentation or packaging segmentation of a construction work related to business qualifications, namely (a) the level of small risk, medium risk, and large risk; (b) simple technology, intermediate technology, and high technology, (c) low cost, medium cost, big cost. This is because after the issuance of Presidential Decree 12 of 2021 concerning PBJP, it only mentions cost and complexity parameters, does not mention risk and technology parameters. So this becomes material to

analyze further the implementation of PBJP based on the Electronic Procurement System (e-procurement) in Tanah Laut Regency for further study of the construction services packaging segmentation after the issuance of Perpres No. 12/2021.

II. METHOD

Arrangements regarding construction services are regulated in detail in accordance with the transitional provisions which state that when Perpres No. 12/2021 comes into force, the Procurement of Construction Works/Procurement of Construction Consultancy Services/Integrated Construction Works will continue to be carried out in accordance with: (a) Permen PUPR No 14/2020 concerning Standards and Guidelines for Procurement of Construction Services Through Providers and implementing regulations; and (b) Permen PUPR No 25/2020 concerning Standards and Guidelines for Procurement of Integrated Construction Works of Design and Build Through Providers and implementing regulations, until the issuance of Regulation of the Head of Institution regarding Procurement of Construction Works/Procurement of Construction Consulting Services/Integrated Construction Works.

Based on the current conditions, which Perpres No. 16/2018 has undergone changes, namely Perpres No. 12/2021 and has been in effect since the date of promulgation on February 2, 2021. So one of the changes, What is quite significant is that in PerpresNo. 12 of 2021, the Government increased the limit on the procurement package for SMEs to six times the previous value of only Rp. 2,500,000,000, - to Rp. 15,000,000,000,- can be seen in detail regarding the different segmentation of construction service packaging according to the Presidential Decree PBJP.

Data Analysis Techniques Test the validity of the data in the study, emphasizing the validity and reliability tests. In quantitative research, the main criteria for research data are valid, reliable and objective. Validity is the degree of accuracy between the data that occurs in the object of research and the power that can be reported by the researcher. Thus, valid data is data "that is not different" and between data reported by researchers and data that actually occurs in the object of research. If the researcher makes a report that is not in accordance with what happened to the object, then the data can be declared invalid.

Table 1 Construction Packaging Segmentation Difference Matrix Perpres PBJP

Perpres No 16/2018	Perpres No 12/2021
<p>1. Small business consists of Micro and Small Business.</p> <p>2. In the procurement of goods/services, PA/KPA expand the participation of small businesses.</p> <p>3. Packaging is carried out by stipulating as many packages as possible for small businesses without neglecting the principles of efficiency, fair business competition, unified system, and quality of technical capabilities.</p> <p>4. The value of the package for the procurement of goods/construction work/other services is a maximum of IDR 2,500,000,000.00 (two billion five hundred million rupiah), reserved for small businesses, except for work packages that require technical capabilities that cannot be met by small business.</p> <p>5.LKPP and Ministries/Institutions/Local Governments expand the participation of small businesses by listing the goods/services produced by small businesses in an electronic catalog.</p> <p>6 .Non-small business providers who carry out the work may conduct business cooperation with small businesses in the form of partnerships, subcontracts, or other forms of cooperation, if there are small businesses that have the ability in the relevant field</p>	<p>1. Small business consists of Micro and Small Business.</p> <p>2.Ministries/Institutions/Local Governments are required to use small business products and cooperatives from domestic production.</p> <p>3.Ministries/Institutions/Regional Governments as referred to in paragraph (2) must allocate at least 40% (forty percent) of the budget value for goods/services expenditures of Ministries/Institutions/Regional Governments.</p> <p>4. Packages for the procurement of goods/construction work/other services with a budget ceiling value of up to Rp. 15,000,000,000.00 (fifteen billion rupiahs) are intended for small businesses and/or cooperatives.</p> <p>5. The value of the procurement budget ceiling as referred to in paragraph (4) is excluded for work packages that require technical capabilities that cannot be met by small businesses and cooperatives.</p> <p>6. The ministry that carries out government affairs in the field of cooperatives and small businesses and the local government expands the participation of small businesses and cooperatives by listing the goods/services produced by small businesses in an electronic catalog.</p> <p>7. Non-small business providers or cooperatives that carry out the work of conducting business cooperation with small businesses and/or cooperatives in the form of partnerships, subcontracts, or other forms of cooperation, if there is a small business or cooperative that has the ability in the relevant field.</p> <p>8. Cooperation with small businesses and/or cooperatives.</p>

Previous Research Several previous studies or studies related to the Procurement of Goods/Services include:

1. Vironika (2008) concept of master plan E. Tendering for Construction services in Central Kalimantan.
2. Dedy junaidy (2012) Study of Implementation Barriers to the Implementation of the E-Procurement System Based on PerpresNo. 54 of 2010 in the Procurement of Construction Works.
3. Waluyo (2012) ABT Project Continuity Assessment
4. Khairunnisa Latief (2018) Analysis of the Payment System for Construction Supervisory Consultants
5. Hasvivaldi Azwardhana (2019) Performance Analysis of the Implementation of the Tasks of the Management Consultant of BBPJN XI Banjarmasin
6. Agus Fatahillah (2021) Study of Understanding the Procurement Process of Government Goods/Services Based on PerpresNo. 16 of 2018 in Tapin District.

Based on previous research or studies, updates are carried out regarding the Government's Goods/Services Procurement process considering that currently there is a change in PerpresNo. 16 of 2018 to PerpresNo. 12 of 2021 concerning Government Procurement of Goods/Services in which the Government raises the limitation of procurement packages for SMEs to six times the previous value which was only Rp. 2,500,000,000, - to Rp. 15,000,000,000,000, a very significant increase in packaging segmentation.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Respondents

The next step is to determine the research method, the data needed and the research instrument. The research method used is a quantitative research method by distributing questionnaires containing questions that represent the determination of job packaging segmentation in accordance with the provisions of PerpresNo. 12 of 2021 concerning Amendments to PerpresNo. 16 of 2018 concerning Government Procurement of Goods/Services. This is the answer from the respondent regarding the questionnaire. The research instrument used at this stage is using a questionnaire that will be distributed to respondents. Respondents in this study were actors in the procurement of goods/services who were involved in the process of procuring goods/services up to the handover of work in Tanah Laut Regency. The list of groups of actors in the procurement of government goods/services and the number of research respondents.

Procurement Actors Total (person)

1. Budget User (PA) : 2 person
 2. Budget User Authority (KPA) concurrently Commitment Making Officer (PPK) : 6 person
 3. PPTK : 9 person
 4. UKPBJ Working Group 5 person
 5. Procurement Officer (PP) 5 person
 6. PBJ Expert 1 person
- Total 28 people

B. Validity Test

This study will use validity testing with item-total correlation with Spearman's correlation coefficient. Item-total correlation is a test method by correlating the score of each answer item with the total score of the questionnaire answers. The calculation of this validity test uses the SPSS 25.0 for windows program.

C. Reliability Test

Reliability testing on this research questionnaire is using the Alpha Cronbach formula because the research instrument is in the form of a questionnaire and a graded scale. This reliability test calculation uses the SPSS 25.0 for windows program.

D. Index Analysis

Calculations were carried out on all respondents' answers to each research indicator. In this study using index analysis. To get the tendency of respondents' answers to each influential indicator, the results of the index analysis will describe the level of influence in various categories indicating the level of influence/satisfaction/understanding, it will be based on the average score (index) which is categorized into a range of scores.

$$\{(fss \times 5) + (fs \times 4) + (fc \times 3) + (fs \times 2) + (fts \times 1)\} \setminus N$$

fss : The answer choices strongly agree;

fs : Answer options agree

fc : The answer choices are quite agree

fks : The answer choices do not agree

fts : The answer choices strongly disagree

N : Number of respondents

Example of index analysis calculation:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Index analysis} &= \{(fss \times 5) + (fs \times 4) + (fc \times 3) + (fks \times 2) + (fts \times 1)\} \setminus N \\ &= \{(5 \times 5) + (10 \times 4) + (10 \times 3) + (3 \times 2) + (0 \times 1)\} \setminus 28 \\ &= 3.60 \end{aligned}$$

Categories of index intervals

Category (Influence/Satisfaction Level) Index Interval

Very Influential = (4.21 – 5.00)

Influential = (3.41 – 4.20)

Just = (2.61 – 3.40)

Boost = (1.81 – 2.60)

Need to Improve = (1.00 – 1.80)

E. Strategy recommendations

The results of data processing from index analysis will be compiled with strategic recommendations that are categorized into score ranges so that an overview of all the data obtained in the research carried out by strategic steps will support the achievement of increasing and optimal level of influence/satisfaction/understanding categories.

IV. ANALYSIS RESULTS

A. Respondents Research Variables and Indicators

Research variable is something in the form of anything that is determined by the researcher to be studied so that information is obtained about it and then conclusions are drawn. These variables and indicators are obtained from a number of regulations related to the packaging of construction work previously described, namely

1. Law Number 2 of 2017 concerning Construction Services;
2. Government Regulation Number 22 of 2020 concerning Implementing Regulations of Law No. 2 of 2017 concerning Construction Services as amended to Government Regulation Number 14 of 2021 concerning Amendments to Government Regulation Number 22 of 2020 concerning Implementation of Law No. 2 of 2017 concerning Construction Services ;
3. Perpres Number 12 /2021 concerning Amendments to Perpres Number 16 of 2018 concerning Procurement of Government Goods/Services;
4. Regulation of the Government Goods/Services Procurement Policy Agency Number 12 of 2021 concerning Guidelines for the Implementation of Government Procurement of Goods/Services Through Providers;
5. Regulation of the Government Goods/Services Procurement Policy Agency Number 11 of 2021 concerning Guidelines for Planning for Government Procurement of Goods/Services.

From some of these rules, there are article clauses regulated in the regulations relating to the determination of packaging segmentation and show that the determination of packaging is not only based on the variable cost, but also other variables. The classification division of research variables can be seen in Table IV.1 for Classification Construction Packaging Variables based on the Level of Complexity and Table IV.2 for the classification of Construction Packaging Variables based on the Level of Risk, Cost, Technology. And Table IV.3 Classification of Indicators in the study.

B. Validity test

The validity test is intended to test the validity of the data in the research process carried out. Validity indicates the level of validity of the research instrument on the results of respondents' answers to the distributed questionnaire. This study will use validity testing with item-total correlation with Spearman's correlation coefficient. Item-total correlation is a test method by correlating the score of each answer item with the total score of the questionnaire answers. According to Sugiyono (2007), Spearman's correlation is used to find or test significant hypotheses if each of the variables connected is ordinal and the data sources between variables are not the same. The validity test formula can be described as follows:

$$r_s = 1 - \frac{(6d_1^2)}{n(n^2-1)}$$

Where is the Spearman correlation coefficient, l^2 is the difference between the two ranks and n is the number of respondents who answered the questionnaire. The results of the validity test of the questions can be seen from the correlation coefficient value of each question instrument. A question is declared valid if r count is greater than the specified r table. To find out the r table, we will use an alpha value of 5% (0.05). Calculations on the validity test will be carried out with the help of the SPSS program. The calculation of this validity test uses the SPSS 25.0 for windows program.

C. Reliability Test

Reliability test was conducted to determine the level of reliability of a research instrument. Reliability (reliability) simply means to withstand the test or can be trusted. An evaluation tool is considered reliable (reliable) or resistant to testing, if it has constant results even though it is carried out several times at different times. Reliability testing on this research questionnaire is using the Alpha Cronbach formula because the research instrument is in the form of a questionnaire and a graded scale. Cronbach's Alpha formula is as follows:

$$r = \frac{(n-1)}{(n-1)} \left(\frac{\Sigma^2}{\sigma_i^2} \right)$$

where l_1 is the reliability sought, n is the number of question items tested, is the sum of the variance scores of each item. The instrument is said to be reliable if r count is greater than or equal to r table. If r count is smaller than r table the instrument is said to be unreliable or the value of r count is consulted with the interpretation table of r with the provision that it is said to be reliable if r count 0.600. This reliability test calculation uses the SPSS 25.0 for windows program.

Table 2 Classification of indicators in research

No	Variable	Indikator		PP No 22 /2020	Perpres PBJ 12/2021	Perlem LKPP 12/2021	Perlem LKPP 11/2021
1	Variable Costs	Ability to determine the amount of work costs needed to complete the work. (X ₁₁)		Article 34 paragraph 4	Article 65 paragraph 4	attachment Perlem 12/2021	attachment Perlem 11/2021
		Ability to understand the impact of setting packages that require technical capabilities that cannot be met by small and micro businesses (X ₁₂)		Article 67 Paragraph 1	Article 65 Paragraph 5	Attachment Perlem 12/2021	Attachment Perlem 11/2021
		Ability to set packaging policies. (X ₁₃)		Article 60, Article 112	Article 5	Attachment Perlem 12/2021	Attachment Perlem 11/2021
		Ability to define packaging for small and micro businesses (X ₁₄)			Article 65 Paragraph 1	Attachment Perlem 12/2021	Attachment Perlem 11/2021
2	Risk Level Variable	Ability to determine the criteria for the level of risk of a construction work (X ₂₁)		Article 34 Paragraph 1	Article 44 Paragraph 10		
		Ability to understand the influence of the scope of work with the level of risk (X ₂₂)		Article 34 Paragraph 2 letter a			
		Ability to understand the influence of the location of the implementation of the work with the level of risk (X ₂₃)		Article 34 Paragraph 2 letter b			
		Ability to understand the influence of labor resource requirements with the level of risk (X ₂₄)		Article 34 Paragraph 2 letter c			
		Ability to understand the effect of the amount of cost with the level of risk (X ₂₅)		Article 35, 36, 37			
3	Technology Level Variable	Ability to determine the technology level criteria of a construction work (X ₃₁)		Article 34 Paragraph 1	Article 44 Paragraph 10		
		Ability to understand the influence of work material requirements with technological level (X ₃₂)		Article 34 Paragraph 3 letter a			
		Ability to understand the influence of work equipment requirements with technology level (X ₃₃)		Article 34 Paragraph 3 letter b			

		Ability to understand the effect of work execution methods with technology level (X ₃₄)		Article 34 Paragraph 3 letter d			
		Ability to understand the influence of the level of technology on the complexity of the work (X ₃₅)		Article 35, 36, 37			
4	Complexity Variable	Ability to determine criteria work complexity (X ₄₁)		Article 35, 36, 37	Article 44 Paragraph 10	Attachment Perlem 12/2021	
		Ability to understand the influence of the level of job risk with the complexity of the job (X ₄₂)		Article 35, 36, 37	Article 44 Paragraph 10	Attachment Perlem 12/2021	
		Ability to understand the effect of cost and work complexity related complexity (X ₄₃)			Article 44 Paragraph 10	Attachment Perlem 12/2021	
		Ability to understand the determination of tender evaluation methods related to the complexity of the work (X ₄₄)		Article 63 dan Article 65	Article 40 Paragraph 1,2,3,4	Attachment Perlem 12/2021	
		Ability to understand construction work qualification requirements (X ₄₅)		Article 63	Article 44	Attachment Perlem 12/2021	

D. Questionnaire Result Data

Based on the results of the literature review in Chapter II, the following variables were obtained including Cost Variables, Risk Level Variables, Technology Level Variables, and Complexity Level Variables and in detail as mentioned for the indicators as mentioned in Subchapter 4.2 Research Variables and Indicators section Table IV.3. The way to answer the questionnaire is to put a checklist (√) on one of the most appropriate answers according to the respondent and the detailed assessment results can be seen in Appendix A. The assessment is carried out based on a scale of 1 to 5 which has the following meanings:

Scale 5 for SS = Strongly Agree

Scale 4 for S = Agree

Scale 3 for CS = Fairly Agree

Scale 2 for KS = Disagree

Scale 1 for STS = Strongly Disagree

The answer data from the respondents' results can be seen in Table 3 Recapitulation of Questionnaire Results Data below.

Table 3 Questionnaire Result Data Recapitulation

No	Variable	Indikator	Respondent's Answer					T Σ
			STS	KS	CS	S	SS	
1.	Costing	X _{1.1}	-	-	12	14	2	28
		X _{1.2}	-	1	6	17	4	28
		X _{1.3}	-	-	12	13	3	28
		X _{1.4}	-	2	8	12	6	28
2.	Risk Determination	X _{2.1}	-	-	15	12	1	28
		X _{2.2}	-	1	10	13	4	28
		X _{2.3}	-	-	4	16	8	28
		X _{2.4}	-	-	11	13	4	28
		X _{2.5}	-	-	14	10	4	28
3.	Technology Determination	X _{3.1}	-	-	14	10	4	28
		X _{3.2}	-	-	12	13	3	28
		X _{3.3}	-	1	9	14	4	28
		X _{3.4}	-	1	10	13	4	28
		X _{3.5}	-	-	8	16	4	28
4.	Complexity Determination	X _{4.1}	-	-	14	10	4	28
		X _{4.2}	-	1	6	17	4	28
		X _{4.3}	-	-	15	12	1	28
		X _{4.4}	-	1	8	13	6	28
		X _{4.5}	-	1	10	13	4	28

E. Validity and Reliability Test

		X _{4.5}	0.82	Valid
--	--	------------------	------	-------

1. Validity Test

Furthermore, the results of the validation of variables can be tested by comparing the correlation coefficient of Spearman's rank with the critical value in question. The critical value referred to at 0.05 is 0.37. From the results of the validity test on 28 respondents as shown in Table 4 Validity Test Results regarding the study of Construction Work packaging segmentation, it is known that the Spearman Rank correlation coefficient (R) is greater than the critical value (R_{0.05} = 0.37) in detail the analysis can be seen in appendix C, so it can be concluded that all items are valid.

Table 4 Validity Test Results

No	Variable	Indikator	R	Conclusion
1.	Costing	X _{1.1}	0.64	Valid
		X _{1.2}	0.84	Valid
		X _{1.3}	0.76	Valid
		X _{1.4}	0.84	Valid
2.	Risk Determination	X _{2.1}	0.71	Valid
		X _{2.2}	0.85	Valid
		X _{2.3}	0.73	Valid
		X _{2.4}	0.81	Valid
		X _{2.5}	0.72	Valid
3.	Technology Determination	X _{3.1}	0.81	Valid
		X _{3.2}	0.77	Valid
		X _{3.3}	0.73	Valid
		X _{3.4}	0.80	Valid
		X _{3.5}	0.79	Valid
4.	Complexity Determination	X _{4.1}	0.77	Valid
		X _{4.2}	0.81	Valid
		X _{4.3}	0.63	Valid
		X _{4.4}	0.84	Valid

2. Reliability Test

The reliability test was carried out by comparing Cronbach's alpha (α) with the minimum value of reliability. If the value of > 0.60 means reliability. The results of the reliability test produce Table 5 regarding the results of the reliability test.

Table 5 Reliability Test Results

No	Variable	Indikator	A	Conclusion
1.	Costing	X _{1.1}	0.95	Reliabel
		X _{1.2}	0.94	Reliabel
		X _{1.3}	0.94	Reliabel
		X _{1.4}	0.94	Reliabel
2.	Risk Determination	X _{2.1}	0.95	Reliabel
		X _{2.2}	0.94	Reliabel
		X _{2.3}	0.95	Reliabel
		X _{2.4}	0.94	Reliabel
		X _{2.5}	0.94	Reliabel
3.	Technology Determination	X _{3.1}	0.94	Reliabel
		X _{3.2}	0.94	Reliabel
		X _{3.3}	0.94	Reliabel
		X _{3.4}	0.94	Reliabel
		X _{3.5}	0.94	Reliabel
4.	Complexity Determination	X _{4.1}	0.94	Reliabel
		X _{4.2}	0.94	Reliabel
		X _{4.3}	0.95	Reliabel
		X _{4.4}	0.94	Reliabel
		X _{4.5}	0.94	Reliabel

From the test results, it can be seen that all obtained are greater than the minimum reliability value can be seen in appendix D, so that all research question items are declared reliable so that the responses from respondents will vary because each has a different opinion, not because confusing and multi-interpreted questionnaire.

Table 6 Data recapitulation of variable categories based on index values

No	Variable	Indicator	Index Value	Influence Level
1.	Costing	X _{1,1}	3.64	Take effect
		X _{1,2}	3.86	Take effect
		X _{1,3}	3.68	Take effect
		X _{1,4}	3.79	Take effect
2.	Risk Determination	X _{2,1}	3.50	Take effect
		X _{2,2}	3.71	Take effect
		X _{2,3}	4.14	Take effect
		X _{2,4}	3.75	Take effect
		X _{2,5}	3.64	Take effect
3.	Technology Determination	X _{3,1}	3.64	Take effect
		X _{3,2}	3.68	Take effect
		X _{3,3}	3.75	Take effect
		X _{3,4}	3.71	Take effect
		X _{3,5}	3.86	Take effect
4.	Complexity Determination	X _{4,1}	3.64	Take effect
		X _{4,2}	3.85	Take effect
		X _{4,3}	3.50	Take effect
		X _{4,4}	3.86	Take effect
		X _{4,5}	3.71	Take effect

In general, all indicators show satisfactory results, which means that the overall level of influence of changes in the construction service packaging segmentation on the PBJP implementation process in Tanah Laut Regency is in accordance with Perpresno. 12 of 2021 as expected, however, attention needs to be paid to the indicators that show the lowest scores on the grounds that there is a possibility that these values will decrease or worsen in the future, based on the results of the lowest scores on each variable and the indicators show that the scores lowest on questions related to regulated

provisions other than the provisions of Perpres No. 12 of 2021 concerning PBJP. Thus, the approach developed needs to focus on the lowest-value indicators in each or every aspect of the performance.

F. Strategic Direction in determining Construction Work Packaging Segmentation

1. The amount of the cost This performance improvement must be directed at efforts to increase understanding through socialization/learning in stages to related parties in this case PA/KPA/PPK/Pokja UKPBJ and PBJP officials that according to the regulations of the Construction Services Act and its derivatives there are variables in addition to the cost of packaging construction work, it is related to the scope of work whether the technical capabilities can be met by small and micro businesses.
2. Risk Level This performance improvement must be directed at efforts to increase understanding through socialization/learning in stages to related parties in this case PA/KPA/PPK/Pokja UKPBJ and PBJP Officials that according to the regulations of the Construction Services Act and its derivatives there are variables the level of risk in packaging construction work, in which the risk criteria are determined based on the following aspects: a. scope of work; b. location of work execution; and c. the need for manpower resources.
3. Technological Level This performance improvement must be directed at efforts to increase understanding through socialization/learning in stages to related parties in this case PA/KPA/PPK/Pokja UKPBJ and PBJP officials that in accordance with the Construction Services Act and its derivatives there are variables technology level in packaging construction work, in which the technology criteria are determined based on the following aspects: a. material; b. equipment; c. experts; and D. implementation method

V. CONCLUSION

1. Effect of PerpresNo. 12 of 2021 Regarding the Packaging of Construction Works in Tanah Laut Regency, several variables were obtained, namely Variables of Cost, Level of Risk, Level of Technology, and Complexity of Work. Each of these variables is then stated in several measurable performance indicators.
2. Through the measurement of the indicators on these variables, it is obtained that the overall Study of the Effect of PerpresNo. 12 of 2021 on the Packaging of Construction Works in Tanah Laut Regency, the level of influence can be categorized as satisfactory, although special attention is given to the indicators with the lowest scores.
3. Starting from the indicators with the lowest score, a number of strategic directions were drawn up in determining the Construction Work Packaging Segmentation. These are assigned to each Variable Cost, Level of Risk, Level of Technology, and Complexity of Work. In determining the packaging of work not only look at the amount of costs but also pay attention to elements of technology, risk and complexity

VI. SUGGESTIONS

1. The research can be expanded to further analyze the role of packaging by PA/KPA associated with the range of control of their authority which requires PBJP contract engagement as a result of the attribution of regional financial management technical guidelines
2. This research can be expanded to include the Provincial Government or Regency/City Government, Ministries or other Institutions outside the Tanah Laut Regency Government to see behavioral patterns in the Ministry/Institution/Regional Apparatus, along with related factors.
3. Further research can be expanded to include making Standard Operational Procedures for the stages after packaging construction work which is part of the PBJP Planning including PBJP Preparation and PBJP Implementation so that it becomes a reference for PBJP actors in the implementation of construction.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Agus Fatahillah (2021) Study of Understanding the Procurement Process of Government Goods/Services Based on PerpresNo. 16 of 2018 in Tapin Regency
- [2]. Mustafa, Khalid; Bawono, Indro;. (2021). Consolidation of Perpres No. 12/2021 with Presidential Decree No. 16 of 2018. Jakarta: Association of Indonesian Procurement Research Centers for Goods or Services
- [3]. Nursetyo, Gatot. (2013). Analysis of Procurement of Goods and Consulting Services (Case Study of Government Projects). Journal of Civil and Architectural Engineering, Universitas Tunas Pembangunan Surakarta.
- [4]. Trisasongko Widiyanto (2021). Construction Bulletin Edition 1 2021. Ministry of Public Works and Public Housing.
- [5]. Indonesian government. 2017. Law Number 2 of 2017 concerning Construction Services (State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia of 2017 Number 11);
- [6]. Indonesian government. 2020. Government Regulation Number 22 of 2020 concerning Implementing Regulations of Law No. 2 of 2017 concerning Construction Services (State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia Year 2020 Number 107);
- [7]. Indonesian government. 2021. PerpresNumber 12 of 2021 concerning Amendments to PerpresNumber 16 of 2018 concerning Procurement of Government Goods/Services (State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia Year 2021 Number 63);
- [8]. Indonesian government. 2021. Regulation of the Government Goods/Services Procurement Policy Agency Number 12 of 2021 concerning Guidelines for the Implementation of Government Procurement of Goods/Services Through Providers
- [9]. Indonesian government. 2021. Regulation of the Government Goods/Services Procurement Policy Institute Number 11 of 2021 concerning Guidelines for Planning for the Procurement of Government Goods/Services (State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia of 2021 Number 512);
- [10]. Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government (State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia of 2014 Number 244, Supplement to the State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia Number 5587) as has been amended several times, most recently by Law Number 9 of 2015 concerning the Second Amendment to Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government (State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia of 2015 Number 58, Supplement to the State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia Number 5679);
- [11]. Law Number 11 of 2020 concerning Job Creation (Supplement to the State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia Number 6573)
- [12]. Government Regulation Number 12 of 2019 concerning Regional Financial Management (State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia of 2019 Number 42, Supplement to the State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia Number 6322)
- [13]. Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia Number 77 of 2020 concerning Technical Guidelines for Regional Financial Management (State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia of 2020 Number 1781)